

Becoming Your Opponent: A Qualitative Analysis of Body Swapping in an Argument About Responses to Climate Change

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Abstract

Embodied perspective-taking in virtual reality (VR) offers new possibilities for conflict resolution by enabling participants to inhabit another's viewpoint. In this study, we introduce a VR role-play paradigm in which participants engage in a structured debate and, midway through, experience a full body-swap with their interlocutor. This immersive intervention aims to go beyond verbal argumentation to create an embodied shift in perspective. We conducted a controlled experiment with 54 participants assigned to either a body-swap condition or a control condition without avatar exchange. Using a combination of post-session questionnaires, essay reflections, and multi-method sentiment analysis, we assessed the impact of the intervention on feeling of presence, embodiment, and perspective-taking. Interestingly, participants in the body-swap condition exhibited significantly lower sentiment in their reflections, suggesting that such interventions may provoke cognitive dissonance or productive discomfort rather than immediate affective alignment. A cluster analysis of responses revealed a spectrum of engagement, with some participants perceiving the experience as disorienting and others as powerfully immersive. While the debate topic of air travel and climate responsibility served as a contextual frame, our findings speak more broadly to the psychological and methodological implications of VR-based body-swapping as a tool for social perspective-taking and experiential learning.

Keywords

Virtual Reality (VR); Embodied Perspective-Taking; Body-Swap; Conflict Resolution; Role-Play Simulation; Social Cognition; Sentiment Analysis; Empathy; Human-Computer Interaction (HCI);

1 Introduction

Global environmental challenges, ranging from resource depletion and biodiversity loss to extreme weather events, are among the most pressing drivers of social tension in the twenty-first

century. As communities grapple with disputes over water rights, land use, and energy policy, traditional negotiation frameworks often fall short of capturing the complex interplay of ecological systems, societal values, and power dynamics. VR has emerged as a promising medium to bridge this gap, allowing stakeholders to engage experientially rather than abstractly. In particular, body-swapping techniques in VR enable users to inhabit the perspectives of opposing parties, fostering cognitive empathy and emotional resonance in ways that tabletop or video-based methods cannot match. By situating participants within realistic, controlled climate-policy scenarios and dynamically equalizing speaking time, VR offers a novel avenue for cultivating equitable dialogue and collaborative problem-solving.

Role-play has been a foundational tool in conflict resolution education for decades. Early studies demonstrated that structured simulations significantly enhance participants' negotiation tactics and self-efficacy in adversarial settings (Andrew & Meligrana, 2012). When playful elements are embedded, these exercises reduce interpersonal tension and foster collaborative mindsets, even among initially reluctant groups (Snodgrass & Blunt, 2009). In secondary-school contexts, drama-based role-play interventions yield measurable gains in empathy and perspective-taking, equipping adolescents to understand and engage with opposing viewpoints (Graves et al., 2007). Social-psychology theories further show that "stepping into another's shoes" can recategorize group identities and diminish intergroup bias (Gaertner et al., 1993; Galinsky et al., 2008).

The possibility of using VR inexpensively and portably has opened new frontiers for role-play methodologies. By placing users in lifelike scenarios and allowing them to embody conflicting roles, VR deepens both moral reasoning and emotional engagement beyond what is possible in tabletop or stage-based exercises (Hasler et al., 2021). Large-scale comparisons indicate that VR perspective-taking leads to more durable increases in empathy compared to traditional methods, with effects observable weeks after the intervention (Herrera et al., 2018). Moreover, VR affords precise control over environmental variables, such as resource distribution, power dynamics, and even the perceived laws of physics, allowing researchers to isolate key drivers of conflict in ways that physical simulations cannot (Wehlan & Reinke, 2022).

Escalating climate change adds an urgent new dimension to conflict-resolution training. Resource scarcity, population displacement, and polarized policy debates are already intensifying disputes, particularly in vulnerable regions (Xie et al., 2024). Scholars of conflict resolution emphasize the need for interventions that go beyond conventional role definitions to actively foster perspective-taking among participants. Traditional programs often overlook unequal participation and rarely employ real-time embodiment techniques. To address these shortcomings, we implemented a body-swapping feature in our VR-based role-play application and conducted a controlled experiment with 54 participants assigned to either a body-swap condition or a control condition. In the body-swap condition, participants halfway through the discussion switched their realistic virtual avatars with their counterpart, while in the control they experienced an equivalent break without embodiment change. Both groups engaged in two five-minute rounds of discussion, arguing about whether to reduce the amount of flights we take, in order to reduce our carbon footprint and overall emissions as individuals. We hypothesized that the body-swap manipulation would amplify perspective-taking and conflict compared to control, leading to more equitable and collaborative outcomes. In the sections that follow, we first review prior work on (1) traditional role-play and serious games, (2) foundational conflict-resolution

and social-psychology theories, (3) VR-mediated interventions and moral judgment, and (4) embodied perspective-taking and empathy in VR. Building on these clusters, we then describe our system's design, experimental deployment, and results of the experiment.

2 Related Work

2.1 Foundational Conflict & Social-Psychology Frameworks

Understanding the psychological underpinnings of intergroup conflict is essential for designing effective interventions. Decades of social-psychology research have identified mechanisms by which group identities form, biases emerge, and empathetic understanding can be fostered. Allport's seminal work on *The Nature of Prejudice* established that social categorization fosters ingroup favoritism and outgroup stereotyping, creating the psychological distance that underlies many conflicts (Allport et al., 1954). Building on this, Turner et al., (1979) showed that simple social comparisons can magnify group-based interests, while Hogg & Turner (1987) demonstrated that salient social identities drive self-stereotyping and polarization. Together, these studies explain why realignment of social categories—such as recategorizing adversaries under a superordinate identity—can reduce bias and open pathways for cooperation.

Gaertner et al.'s Common Ingroup Identity Model articulates precisely this recategorization mechanism: by shifting participants from “us versus them” to a shared “we,” individuals lower intergroup barriers and become more receptive to collaborative solutions (Gaertner et al., 1993). (Galinsky et al., 2008) extended these insights into negotiation contexts, showing that perspective-taking exercises, efforts to vividly imagine another's viewpoint, sharpen understanding of opponents' motivations and lead to more integrative, less zero-sum bargaining. From a neuroscience perspective, Decety & Meyer (2008) delineated how emotional resonance (automatic mirroring of others' affect) and cognitive perspective-taking (deliberate inference of mental states) jointly contribute to empathic understanding, a process Decety (2005) called the “royal avenue” to empathy.

2.2 Role-Play & Serious Games

Transforming theory into practice, researchers have long employed structured role-play and serious games to teach conflict-management and negotiation skills. While foundational studies have established role-play's value, subsequent work has refined how its mechanics can be optimized. Catterall (2007) demonstrated that structured drama exercises yield measurable improvements in peer-mediation outcomes, with participants reporting clearer communication strategies and higher resolution rates. Extending this, Shaikh et al., (2023) showed that iterative “rehearsal” of negotiation scenarios strengthens long-term skill retention, suggesting that repetition under varied stakes embeds conflict-management tactics. Recent work has infused these practices with creative narratives: Wehlan & Reinke (2022) introduced “fantastical” simulations blending real-world issues with imaginative storylines to boost engagement and reinforce learning. Cheong et al., (2015) added serious-game dashboards that visualize concession patterns and alliance shifts in real time, enabling participants to reflect on strategic choices during play. A foundational tool for tailoring these simulations to individuals' styles is the Thomas-Kilmann MODE instrument (Kilmann & Thomas, 1977). Developed to categorize

conflict-handling preferences along five dimensions (Competing, Collaborating, Compromising, Avoiding, and Accommodating) the MODE questionnaire enables facilitators to diagnose participants' default approaches and adjust scenario roles or stakes accordingly. By matching role assignments to individual profiles, educators can challenge participants to adopt less familiar strategies, thereby broadening their repertoire of conflict-resolution behaviors.

2.3 Embodied VR Perspective-Taking & Empathy

A substantial body of work demonstrates that virtual embodiment, where users inhabit a virtual body different from their own, can powerfully amplify empathetic responses and reduce intergroup bias. In large-scale comparisons Herrera et al., (2018) found that participants who experienced a first-person VR perspective of another individual sustained greater empathy gains up to two weeks post-intervention than those in traditional narrative or 2D video conditions. Similarly, Bertrand et al., (2018) showed that using body-ownership illusions in VR enables multiple training strategies (e.g., synchronized movement, visuo-tactile feedback) that together strengthen participants' capacity to recognize and share others' emotions.

Early foundational studies by Peck et al., (2013) found that embodying a Black avatar through first-person perspective and synchronized movement reduced implicit racial bias for up to one week. Building on this, Banakou et al., (2016) demonstrated that adding visuotactile feedback further sustained bias reduction. However, later work emphasized that these effects are context-dependent: when participants experienced the embodiment under conditions of stress or threat, the intervention could instead increase bias. Maister et al., (2013) extended this insight beyond race, demonstrating that owning another body (even one of a different age or gender) alters participants' social cognition and attitudes toward the embodied group. Oyekoya et al., (2021) found that first-person enactment of bullying scenarios amplifies emotional impact compared to screen-based role-play, enhancing both empathy and self-awareness.

Researchers have also applied these techniques to more targeted social challenges. Christofi et al., (2020). designed a VR simulation that immerses users in the daily experiences of individuals under the influence of substances, demonstrating that navigating obstacles while "intoxicated" increases helping behaviors toward marginalized populations . (Slater et al., 2018) created a historical reenactment by placing participants in the body of Lenin, which significantly boosted users' sense of presence and engagement in educational contexts.

2.4 VR Conflict Resolution & Moral Judgment

Early theoretical frameworks in virtual reality research emphasized presence as a key determinant of behavioral engagement in immersive environments. In particular, Sanchez-Vives & Slater (2005) argued that greater presence, defined as the subjective sense of "being there", increases the likelihood of participants behaving realistically in VR. This foundational insight has since guided the design of VR interventions aiming to foster empathy and social perspective-taking. A growing body of empirical studies and conceptual models has built upon this work to explore VR's influence on moral judgment and conflict engagement. Seinfeld et al., (2018) were

among the first to demonstrate VR's ethical impact, placing participants in offender-and-victim roles within a domestic-violence scenario and finding that this role reversal led to a measurable change in the perception of women's angry facial expressions, suggesting that immersive role reversal can recalibrate social and emotional processing of threat cues. Subsequent meta-analyses and systematic reviews, most recently Tassinari et al., (2022) examined 64 VR studies on prejudice and moral outcomes confirm that embodied immersive experiences consistently foster prosocial judgments and outline methodological best practices for future work. As another example, Canet & Sánchez-Castillo (2024) conducted a systematic review and meta-analysis showing that VR yields moderate to large effect sizes on prosocial outcomes such as helping behavior and cooperative intent. They also identified key design variables that predict these empathy gains; for example, the level of interactivity and the fidelity of the virtual embodiment. Adding a critical perspective, Chen & White (2024) argue that while presence is powerful, research must also look into the long term effect and the real world application of these applications.

2.5 Climate Change & Peacebuilding

The intensification of climate change has spawned a distinct branch of conflict-resolution research focused on environmental disputes and the unique challenges they pose. Xie et al., (2024) provide a comprehensive review of causal pathways linking rising temperatures and extreme weather events to increases in violent conflict, demonstrating that resource scarcity, economic stress, and social disruption each elevate the risk of dispute escalation. Knaster (2010) argue for the centrality of equitable deliberation in environmental negotiations, showing through case studies that mediators who actively manage speaking time and agenda-setting can prevent dominant actors from monopolizing discourse and blocking consensus. However, most existing mediation training relies on tabletop exercises or desktop simulations, offering limited opportunities for participants to viscerally experience the stakes of environmental change or to practice facilitating balance of voice in real time.

Building on this empirical foundation, Krampe et al., (2024) chart an emerging research agenda for climate peacebuilding, identifying sub-themes such as community resilience, adaptive governance, and inclusive dialogue as critical areas for intervention. Their synthesis makes clear that traditional conflict-resolution techniques must be adapted to account for the transboundary, long-term, and deeply systemic nature of climate conflicts.

3. Materials and Methods

This section details the methodology used to test the hypothesis that a body-swapping intervention in virtual reality would enhance perspective-taking in a conflict scenario. We describe a controlled experiment involving 54 participants, who were organized into same-gender dyads and assigned to either an experimental (body-swap) or a control group. Each pair engaged in a VR-based argumentative discussion focused on climate change. The following subsections outline the participant demographics, the experimental design and specific scenario, the equipment used, the step-by-step procedure, and the response variables measured. Furthermore, we describe the extensive sentiment analysis and formal statistical modeling techniques applied to the collected data to assess the intervention's impact.

3.1 Participants and Ethics

Fifty-four participants (27 same-gender dyads) were recruited from the University of Barcelona campus. All participants provided written informed consent and received €15 in compensation. The study protocol was approved by the Comisió de Bioètica de la Universitat de Barcelona, and adhered to its ethical guidelines. The participants were assigned to two conditions: 40 in the Experiment condition and 14 in the Control condition. Each pair of participants engaged in a VR-based argumentative discussion around climate change, followed by an embodied perspective shift intervention.

The gender distribution across conditions is balanced in the Experiment condition (20 male, 20 female), while the Control group included 8 males and 6 females participants. The average age in the Experiment condition was **32.1 years** (SD = 8.45), ranging from 18 to 57. In the Control group, the average was slightly lower at **28.9 years** (SD = 3.50), ranging from 24 to 36.

Occupation Distribution

Participants reported their occupation, categorized as follows:

Table 1 – Distribution of Participants by Occupation

occupation	Experiment (n=40)	Control (n=14)
Employed Full-time	25	7
Employed Part-time	3	1
Self-Employed	5	1
Student	7	5

3.2 Experimental Design and Scenario

Participants took part in a single 25-minute session in one of two between-groups conditions:

- **Experimental (Body-Swap):** Participants argued for 5 minutes from their own perspective, then swapped virtual bodies and argued from their partner's viewpoint for 5 minutes, and finally returned to their own bodies for 5 minutes of reflection.
- **Control (No Swap):** Same timeline but participants simply switched physical positions in the VR world without body-swap functionality.

In both conditions, dyads debated whether taking commercial flights is acceptable behaviour in the face of climate change while sitting in front of opposing posters illustrating “pro-flight” and “anti-flight” positions.

Figure 1 – Example of posters placed behind the participants on the walls.

Figure 2 – Two participants facing each other, as shown in a virtual mirror. Each was represented by a look-alike virtual body, and had posters behind them illustrating their position in the argument.

The shared virtual meeting was enabled by the VR United system (Oliva Martínez et al., n.d.) which is a virtual environment application developed with the QuickVR library (Oliva et al., 2022) and built on the Unity engine. To create the look-alike virtual bodies mentioned in the study, a specialized pipeline was used to generate a lifelike 3D avatar from a single frontal RGB photograph (Beacco et al., 2023) This system utilizes deep learning techniques to extract pose, shape, and semantic information from the input image. This approach allowed for the generation of a personalized avatar for each participant in approximately 30 minutes.

Figure 3 – Virtual meeting room.

3.3 Equipment

All participants wore standalone Pico Neo 3 HMDs (1832×1920 px per eye, 90° FOV, 90 Hz) with 6 DoF controllers and used Skullcandy Riff wireless headphones for stereo sound and active noise cancellation .

3.4 Procedure

The procedure for the experiment involved several distinct steps. Upon arrival, participant was welcomed and directed to read an information sheet on Qualtrics. Before entering the lab, they completed a demographics form and the Thomas-Kilmann Conflict Mode Instrument (Kilmann & Thomas, 1977) to establish their baseline conflict-handling styles.

Following the pre-session questionnaires, participants were guided into the VR lab for a 25-minute session. During this time, they engaged in the debate scenario, subject to either the body-swap or control manipulation.

After the VR exposure, participants completed a set of post-session measures:

- **Essay:** They wrote a 150-500 word free-text response describing their experience.
- **Presence & Copresence Questionnaire:** They rated their sense of being in the virtual world on standardized 1-7 Likert scales.
- **Discussion Quality Questionnaire:** They answered questions about the quality of the discussion, including aspects like participation equality and comfort level.

3.5 Response Variables

The response variables were the data collected from a questionnaire administered after the VR session. This questionnaire was designed to capture the participants' subjective experience and included an essay, measures for presence and copresence, and other questions about the discussion. Table 2 shows the detailed specific variables along with the questions.

Table 2 – The questionnaire based response variables by condition. Each question is on a 1-7 scale. The medians and interquartile ranges are shown.

Variable	Meaning			
essay	Please write a 150-500 word report about your experience. In particular, focus on how much it felt like a face-to-face discussion and your opinion of how the discussion changed over time.			

		Main		Control		Total	
		Median	IQR	Median	IQR	Median	IQR
there	Please rate your sense of being in the virtual environment, on the following scale from 1 to 7, where 7 represents your normal experience of being in a place.	5	1	5	1	5	1
real	To what extent were there times during the experience when the virtual environment was the reality for you?	5	2.25	4.50	1.75	5	2
visited	When you think back about your experience, do you think of the virtual environment more as images that you saw, or more as somewhere that you visited?	3	3	6	1.75	4	4
otherplace	During the time of the experience, which was strongest on the whole, your sense of being in the virtual environment, or of being elsewhere?	5	1	5.50	3.5	5	1.75
copresence	How much did you have a sense of being in the same space with other people?	5.5	1	6	0.75	6	1
topic	I found the discussion topic interesting.	6	2	5	3.5	6	2
discussion	The discussion flowed smoothly and both of us participated equally.	6	2	6.5	2	6	2
comfort	I felt comfortable speaking up and felt listened to.	7	1.25	7	1	7	1
virtuality	The fact that the discussion was virtual didn't take away the quality of it.	6	3	5.5	1.75	6	3

preference	I felt more at ease participating in the discussion than I would in real-life.	4	3	4	2.5	4	3
preferreal	I prefer real-life discussion to virtual discussions.	5	2	4	1.75	5	2

A

B

Figure 4 – Box plots of the presence (A) and social (B) variables by condition.

These results suggest relatively high levels of presence and comfort across both conditions, with the VR environment successfully serving as a backdrop for the discussion. A detailed look at the response variables shows that both groups reported a strong sense of "being there" and that the environment felt "real". On the social side, the application was effective; participants in both groups felt very comfortable speaking up and being listened to, with both conditions reporting a median score of 7 out of 7 on this measure. Similarly, both groups found the discussion topic interesting and agreed that the discussion flowed smoothly with equal participation.

However, there are notable differences between the groups that may reflect the cognitive impact of the body-swapping intervention. The most significant divergence appears in the "visited" variable, where the Control group reported a much stronger sense of having visited a place (Median of 6) compared to the Experimental group (Median of 3). Furthermore, the Control condition reported slightly greater "copresence", a sense of being in the same space with the other person, and their responses were more consistent, as shown by the smaller interquartile range. While both groups felt the virtuality did not detract from the discussion quality, the Experimental group showed a slightly stronger preference for real-life discussions over virtual ones.

3.6. Sentiment Analysis

The purpose here is to analyse the sentiment scores of the individuals, based on comments they wrote on a questionnaire. All comments were translated to English. This technique was used in previous experiments like Slater et al., (2023 and Tütüncü et al., (2025)

Four different methods of sentiment analysis were used:

sentimentr (Rinker, 2021) uses 9 dictionaries and aims particularly at ‘valence shifters’ i.e., modifiers where ‘I do not like it’ is correctly recognized as negative and ‘I really like it’ is an enhanced positive valence. Generally, rather than document-level, it performs sentence-level analysis. As mentioned above, it concentrates on valence shifters, which are words that modify sentiment intensity. Finally, it considers context around sentiment-bearing words.

The **VADER** (Valence Aware Dictionary and Sentiment Reasoner) system (Hutto & Gilbert, 2014) was designed for the analysis of social media text but also is used more generally. It is optimised for social media content and informal communication, dealing with slang, emoticons, acronyms (like "LOL"), and punctuation emphasis ("!!!"). Here we use the R implementation¹ by Katherine Roehrick.

The **syuzhet** package (Jockers, 2017)² includes 4 sentiment lexicons and was originally designed for analysis of the latent structure in narrative, although it has been used widely for other applications. It is designed primarily for narrative analysis and emotional arcs in storytelling. Unlike sentimentr and VADER which focus mainly on general sentiment polarity, syuzhet specializes in identifying emotional content and narrative patterns.

qdap (Quantitative Discourse Analysis Package) (Rinker et al., 2020). This evaluates a basic, general form of sentiment, referred to as valence-based polarity. It does not distinguish between specific types of emotion (like anger, joy, fear, etc.), but rather assigns a polarity score based on: positive words which contribute to a positive score, negative words which contribute to a negative score, and neutral or unknown words which contribute zero.

Table 3 briefly contrasts the 4 packages. It can be seen that each measures different aspects of sentiment.

Table 3 – Comparison of 4 Sentiment Packages Used.

Package	What It Measures	Context Sensitivity	Best For
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¹ <https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=vader>

² <https://github.com/mjockers/syuzhet>

sentimentr	General polarity (positive/negative sentiment) at the sentence level, while accounting for valence shifters (like negators and amplifiers)	Good handling of negation and modifiers	Detailed sentence-level sentiment with context awareness
VADER	General polarity and intensity of sentiment, including social media-style tone (e.g., emojis, slang, all-caps)	Designed for social and informal text	Social media, short-form, and informal text analysis
syuzhet	Narrative sentiment flow (emotional arc over time), plus general sentiment scoring using various lexicons		Analyzing emotional trajectories in stories, speeches, or longer narratives
qdap	Basic positive vs. negative sentiment (polarity), often in transcripts or discourse analysis	Limited (some negation handled)	Quick polarity scoring in interviews, open-ended surveys, transcripts.

3.7 Descriptive Analysis

Figure 5 – Histograms of the 4 density scores.

Figure 5 shows the histograms of the 4 sentiment scores. It can be seen that they are quite different, especially VADER is quite different the other 3.

In order to gain insight into the 4 scores, we first standardize them so that they all have mean 0 and standard deviation 1. Then they are placed in matrix with columns in the same order as in Table 1. Using **kmeans** clustering in R, we partition the individuals into 4 clusters. We chose 4 instead of 5, because with 5 clusters there are overlaps between them).

Table 4 – Standardized Sentiment Scores Over the 4 Clusters

Cluster:	Cluster 1	Cluster 2	Cluster 3	Cluster 4
No. in Cluster	15	11	18	10
sentimentr	-0.542 ± 0.575	-0.854 ± 0.821	0.268 ± 0.549	1.270 ± 0.860
VADER	-1.401 ± 0.573	0.364 ± 0.425	0.530 ± 0.494	0.747 ± 0.320
syuzhet	-0.724 ± 0.613	-0.707 ± 0.378	0.267 ± 0.511	1.383 ± 0.949
qdap	-0.771 ± 0.542	-0.662 ± 0.771	0.375 ± 0.709	1.209 ± 0.626

Table 4 shows the standardized sentiment scores by cluster. It is clear that the higher cluster numbers are associated with more positive sentiment each case.

We can visualize the clusters using the factoextra package in R (Kassambara & Mundt, 2020). This finds the first two principal component scores, and plots 2D versions of the clusters with the first PC on the horizontal axis, and the second on the vertical axis. **Figure 4** shows 4 separated clusters. The first 2 PCs account for 85% of the total variance. Clusters 1, 3 and 4 are separated on the x-axis and cluster 2 is mainly separated from 1 on the y-axis.

Table 5 – Loadings on the 1st two PCs

Sentiment Method	PC1	PC2
sentimentr	0.52	0.52
VADER	0.44	-0.77
syuzhet	0.55	0.31
qdap	0.48	-0.21

Table 5 shows the PC loadings for the first two sentiment method. PC1 has approximately the same loadings for each of the 4 sentiment methods. PC2 shows the contrast – where it is low on sentimentr and qdap.

Table 6 – Percentages of Control and Experimental Groups in the Clusters

Cluster	Control %	Experimental %	No. in Cluster
1	7	35	15
2	21	20	11
3	43	30	18
4	29	15	10

Total	14	40	54
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Table 6 shows the distribution of the Control and Experimental groups by cluster. The Control group tends to be in the higher sentiment clusters - e.g., while 72% of the Control group are in clusters 3 or 4, there are 45% in the Experimental group. Also while 28% of the Control group are in the two lowest clusters, it is 55% of those in the Experimental group. Or, 7% of the Control are the lowest sentiment cluster (1) whereas 35% of the Experimental group. Hence the evidence suggests that the body swapping technique reduces sentiment.

Figure 6 – The 4 clusters represented on the first two principal component scores.

Figure 6 shows word clouds for the 4 clusters, using the packages `udpipe`, `textrank` and `wordcloud` in R. These reflect the earlier finding that generally that positive sentiment is associated with the cluster numbers.

Figure 7 – Word clouds for the 4 clusters

To gain deeper qualitative insight into the sentiment of each cluster, the R package *lexRankr* was used to algorithmically extract the top five most representative sentences from the participants' written comments. The results, presented in Table 7, confirm the initial observation that the discussions focused heavily on the experience of the technology itself, rather than on the affect raised by the climate change argument.

A closer look at the clusters reveals a clear progression in how participants processed the virtual experience. The lower-sentiment clusters (1 and 2) are dominated by reflections on the novelty and difficulty of the intervention. Participants described the body-swap as a "strange sensation" and noted the initial confusion of seeing their own avatar in front of them. Some in these groups expressed a desire to return to a "face-to-face discussion" when they strongly disagreed with their partner, highlighting the limitations of the technology in moments of high conflict.

In contrast, the higher-sentiment clusters (3 and 4) reflect a more seamless integration of the technology into the debate. In Cluster 3, participants described the VR experience as feeling "very natural" and "like a face-to-face discussion but more fun". For those in Cluster 4, the highest-sentiment group, the technology was not a distraction but a powerful tool. They commented that the "discussion felt very real" and that the exercise was a "great way to first consider the position you need to defend". One participant even noted that returning to their own avatar helped them "get into character and argue my stance more convincingly," suggesting they found the virtual embodiment functionally useful for the debate. This progression shows that

while some found the technology to be a strange distraction, others perceived it as an effective and realistic medium for argumentation.

Table 7 – Key sentences from the comments by cluster

Cluster 1	Sentences
1	Switching positions in the middle of the discussion felt very strange.
2	However, toward the end, I felt the need to have a face-to-face discussion with the real person because I strongly disagreed with some of their arguments.
3	Instead, I focused on discussing different perspectives without personalizing the debate.
4	Seeing the other person's position so clearly displayed also influenced my own arguments and slightly shifted my approach to the discussion.
5	At first, seeing my partner as an avatar felt strange and made the environment seem less believable.
Cluster 2	
1	The experience of switching avatars was also strange—seeing my own avatar in front of me felt like debating with another person, and having to suddenly switch opinions added a bit of initial confusion.
2	This was my first time participating in a virtual reality experiment, and at first, the sensation felt a bit strange—I needed a few seconds to adjust to the environment and the avatar.
3	When my partner's avatar appeared and we started the debate, I was surprised by how similar it felt to a face-to-face conversation.
4	At first, it felt quite natural since the opinion I had to defend aligned with my real opinion.
5	I got my topic with no idea how I can defend it because it was hard to try to express my opinion without seeing a person in life.
Cluster 3	
1	The virtual setting distracted us from the content of our conversation and turned the experience into a somewhat comical situation.
2	I have had previous conversations with the other participant in real life and the VR experience felt very natural.
3	Since I could argue with a person that I already know and I could hear her voice and see her avatar, it really felt like a face-to-face discussion but more fun.
4	The experience felt a bit short.
5	It was immersive with the avatar that resembles, I felt very much engaged in the conversation.
Cluster 4	
1	The discussion felt very real, as we were able to present both points of view and switch positions depending on our assigned role.
2	Regarding how my opinion evolved over time, I think this exercise is a great way to first consider the position you need to defend and find the strongest arguments to persuade the other person.
3	The use of virtual reality made this experience feel entirely real.
4	We both made an effort to defend our positions with solid arguments.
5	When I had to defend my initial position in my own avatar, being in my own body helped me get into character and argue my stance more convincingly.

3.8 Formal Analysis

We treat the 4 columns of the matrix which has columns consisting of the 4 sentiment method standardised scores in the same order as above, as the multivariate response variable. From a rough analysis of the results of the Thomas-Kilmann questionnaire it seems that the variable 'competing' had an impact on the results. Table 5 shows that some of the variables computed from this questionnaire are highly correlated. (We show significance indicators only to indicate the strengths of the correlations, not as hypothesis tests).

Table 7 indicates that we cannot choose two variables highly correlated as regressors (e.g., collaborating and avoiding). If we chose avoiding, accommodating and competing this would have the problem that competing and accommodating are correlated.

Table 8 – Pearson Correlations Between the Thomas-Kilmann Questionnaire Variables

	avoiding	accommodating	competing	collaborating	compromising
avoiding	1	0.086	-0.200	-0.534***	-0.301*
accommodating		1	-0.603***	-0.059	-0.369**
competing			1	-0.221	-0.121
collaborating				1	-0.166

For each variable the following gives the number of others that it is *not* correlated with:

- avoiding: 2
- accommodating: 2
- competing: 3
- collaborating: 3
- compromising: 2

This suggests that either competing or collaborating or both could be used as an explanatory variable. However, when both are used collaborating makes no contribution to the model fit, therefore we stay with competing.

The statistical model is Bayesian, with the likelihood as a multivariate Student t distribution, thus allowing for correlations between the response variables.

The model includes group as a random component (i.e., it is multilevel with individual within group).

For each variable the model is a straightforward one with linear predictor:

$$\eta_i = u_{group[i]} + \beta_0 + \beta_1 C_i + \beta_2 competing_i + \beta_3 (C_i \cdot competing_i)$$

$$i = 1, 2, \dots, N = 54$$

$u_{group[i]}$ is the random effect of ‘group’ where $group[i] \in [1, 2, \dots, 27]$

$$C_i = \begin{cases} 0, & \text{Control.} \\ 1, & \text{Experimental} \end{cases}$$

More completely, the model analyses the $K = 4$ sentiment outcomes for N observations nested within $J=27$ groups. For each observation $n \in \{1, \dots, N\}$ and sentiment outcome $k \in \{1, \dots, K\}$, the linear predictor μ_{nk} is defined as:

$$\mu_{nk} = X_n \cdot \beta_k^T + u_{group[n],k}$$

where:

- $X_n \cdot$ is the P -dimensional row vector of predictors for observation n .
- $\beta_k \cdot$ is the P -dimensional row vector of fixed effect coefficients for outcome k .
- u_{jk} is the random effect for group j on outcome k .

The K -dimensional vector of sentiment outcomes for observation n , denoted $y_n = (y_{n1}, \dots, y_{nK})$ is modeled using a multivariate Student-t distribution:

$$y_n \sim \text{MultiStudentT}(v, \mu_n, \Sigma_{res})$$

where:

- $v = 5$ are the degrees of freedom (chosen to have wide prior variation).
- $(\mu_{n1}, \dots, \mu_{nK})$ is the location vector.
- Σ_{res} is the $K \times K$ residual scale matrix.

Priors are:

$$u_{raw,jk} \sim \text{Normal}(0,1)$$

$$u_{jk} = u_{raw,jk} \cdot \tau_k$$

$$\tau_k \sim \text{Cauchy}^+(0,1)$$

(Half-Cauchy for random effect standard deviations for outcome k).

- Residual scales

$$\sigma_k \sim \text{Cauchy}^+(0,2.5)$$

Parameters:

- β_{kp} : Fixed effect of predictor p on sentiment outcome k .
- u_{jk} : Random effect of group j on sentiment outcome k .
- τ_k : Standard deviation of random effects for sentiment k across groups.
- σ_k : Residual standard deviation for sentiment k .
- Σ_{res} : $K \times K$ scale matrix for the multivariate Student-t distribution.

Summaries of the posterior distributions of the parameters are shown in Table 6.

The Experimental condition is associated with *lower* sentimentr (prob = 1 – 0.030 = 0.97), VADER (prob = 1 – 0.009 = 0.991), **syuzhet** (prob = 1 – 0.046 = 0.954) but not qdap.

- Higher values of the variable competing are associated with:
- lower sentimentr in the Control condition (prob = 1 – 0.025 = 0.975), and
- higher sentimentr in the Experimental condition (prob = 0.959).
 - The same is true for VADER (probs = 0.972, 0.940, respectively).
 - The same is true for syuzhet (probs = 0.954, 0.928, respectively).
 - There is no effect for qdap.

The other parameters of interest are the τ_k . Each τ_k represents the **standard deviation of the random effects for the k th sentiment variable across the 4 groups**. In other words it is how much the groups differ from each other for that sentiment. A large τ_k indicates substantial variability in the sentiment k across the 27 groups – i.e., the group identity matters a lot for this sentiment. We can see that τ_3 has a mean much greater than all the others, so that the group structure influenced the **syuzhet** sentiment measure more than all the others. Looking back at Table 1 this is the only one that puts emotion at its core.

The syuzhet method appears to capture the most salient differences between the groups. The way group members expressed themselves might lead to more distinct sentiment scores with syuzhet compared to the other tools. This might make syuzhet a more informative tool – possibly showing how different groups responded to or reflected on the conflict in different emotional ways.

Table 9 – Summaries of the posterior distributions of the parameters. Prob > 0 is the probability that the parameter is positive

Parameter	Coefficient of	Mean	SD	2.5%	97.5%	Prob > 0
sentimentr						
β_0		0.84	0.41	0.05	1.68	0.978
β_1	C(condition)	-0.92	0.48	-1.87	0.00	0.030
β_2	competing	-0.20	0.09	-0.39	-0.02	0.025
β_3	C×competing	0.20	0.11	-0.02	0.42	0.959
VADER						
β_0		1.11	0.42	0.28	1.94	0.994
β_1	C	-1.20	0.49	-2.15	-0.25	0.009
β_2	competing	-0.21	0.10	-0.40	0.00	0.028
β_3	C×competing	0.19	0.12	-0.05	0.42	0.940
syuzhet						
β_0		0.68	0.39	-0.09	1.46	0.955
β_1	C	-0.80	0.45	-1.68	0.09	0.050

β_2	competing	-0.15	0.08	-0.32	0.01	0.046
β_3	C×competing	0.15	0.10	-0.04	0.35	0.928
qdap						
β_0		0.27	0.46	-0.65	1.16	0.736
β_1	C	-0.08	0.54	-1.09	1.01	0.431
β_2	competing	-0.07	0.11	-0.28	0.15	0.236
β_3	C×competing	0.01	0.13	-0.25	0.26	0.535
σ_1		0.84	0.10	0.67	1.05	
σ_2		0.90	0.11	0.71	1.14	
σ_3		0.73	0.09	0.57	0.94	
σ_4		0.92	0.11	0.72	1.15	
τ_1		0.17	0.12	0.01	0.45	
τ_2		0.18	0.13	0.01	0.50	
τ_3		0.41	0.12	0.17	0.65	
τ_4		0.23	0.16	0.01	0.59	

Discussion

The central hypothesis of this study was that using an immersive body-swapping feature in a VR-based conflictual discussion would amplify perspective-taking and foster more collaborative outcomes. We anticipated this might manifest as more positive or integrative language. However, our primary quantitative finding presents a more complex picture. Contrary to our initial expectations, the sentiment analysis revealed that participants in the body-swap (Experimental) condition reported significantly lower positive sentiment in their post-session reflections compared to the control group. This unexpected result requires careful interpretation, as it challenges the simple assumption that perspective-taking exercises should immediately generate positive feelings.

We propose that this reduction in sentiment signals a deeper and more cognitively demanding engagement with the conflict. The qualitative data supports this interpretation; participants in the lower-sentiment clusters frequently described the experience as "strange" or "difficult" and noted the challenge of arguing for a position they disagreed with. This suggests the body-swap induced a state of productive discomfort or cognitive dissonance, forcing participants to grapple more seriously with the opposing viewpoint. In contrast, some high-sentiment comments described the experience as "fun" or "comical", which could imply a more superficial engagement. Therefore, the lower sentiment scores may reflect a more profound, less trivial interaction with the conflict, which is a critical, albeit uncomfortable, step toward genuine understanding.

This interpretation reframes the connection to foundational research. While the goal of perspective-taking is to reduce intergroup bias and move toward a shared "we" identity, our findings suggest the path to that outcome via an immediate positive affect. The process of "walking a mile" in another's shoes may be psychologically taxing, and our sentiment analysis appears to have captured the immediate cognitive cost of that difficult exercise. By forcing an embodied confrontation with an opposing view, the intervention may have tempered

superficially positive reactions in favor of a more challenging and ultimately more meaningful form of engagement.

Several limitations should be noted. Our sample comprised predominantly university-affiliated dyads, a demographic likely predisposed to collaboration and with above-average digital literacy. Xue et al.'s scoping review showed that bystander behaviors in interpersonal violence simulations differ substantially between student and community samples (Xue et al., 2021). Future replications should recruit local government officials or community activists to test ecological validity. Another limitation is our single-session design. VR effects often attenuate over time unless reinforced by longitudinal practice. Integrating intergenerational storytelling approaches, such as LegacySphere, could sustain empathy gains by tying role-play reflections to participants' lived histories (Shen et al., 2024).

Looking forward, several promising avenues emerge. First, expanding embodiment domains beyond human avatars could help participants "become" ecological entities, such as polar bears or drought-affected farmers, to deepen environmental empathy. Future work should explore cross-cultural applications, building on (Galvan Debarba et al., 2017) who characterized first- and third-person alternations in diverse VR contexts, to ensure that climate dialogues remain inclusive across global regions.

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